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**FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT
IN ENGINEERING
SCIENCES**

Community Meeting CC-41, March 3rd, 2022

Kevin Logan, Michaela Leštáková, Ina Heine, Thomas Stäcker, Peter Pelz
NFDI4Ing / RWTH Aachen / TU Darmstadt

**FAIR Data Management
in Engineering
Sciences**

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**discussed
and presented
in a FAIR Journal**

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SCIENTIFIC CREDIT

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data governance

data economics

data ethics

data sets

data management software

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non-academic research

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libraries

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tu datalib

tu prints

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